
SACKVILLE GARDENS, MANCHESTER

REPORT ON AN ARCHAEOLOGICAL INVESTIGATION

July - August 2025

Sackville Gardens Community Excavation 2025

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1.0 Abstract

A community archaeological investigation was undertaken, led by a team of supervisors affiliated to the University of York, between July and August 2025 in Sackville Gardens, Manchester. This excavation was undertaken as part of a PhD research project at the University of York; ‘Trowel, Trenches, and #TransRights: Archaeology and Transgender Activism’. The PhD project is being led by Owen Hurcum and supervised by Doctor Colleen Morgan and Professor Emma Waterton.

The excavation was funded by the UKRI Arts and Humanities Research Council through the White Rose College of the Arts and Humanities (WRoCAH), The Leverhulme Trust, and the Heritage for Global Challenges Research Centre (HGCRC) (the work was partly funded by Professor Emma Waterton's Leverhulme International Professorship [LIP-2022-003]). Equipment was loaned by the Department of Archaeology at the University of York. Further project partners included Manchester City Council through the Manchester Park Rangers, and the Friends of Sackville Gardens, who granted permission for the excavation to be conducted.

Three trenches were excavated during the fieldwork period. Excavation revealed evidence of late 20th century public life in Manchester, potential activities related to subaltern cultures such as the homeless and LGBTQ+ community, features of the Garden's original Edwardian layout, and 19th century industrial activity and destruction.

Figure 1. Site Location (SJ 84432 97801) in Manchester, 1:10 000

Figure 2. Site Boundary within Sackville Gardens and the immediate location of Sackville Gardens in Manchester.

2.0 Site Location, Land Use, Geology and Topography

The excavation site lies within the boundaries of Sackville Gardens, Manchester, which is centered at National Grid Reference SJ 84432 97801.

The area of the excavation is situated towards the Northern corner of the Gardens, bordering the Rochdale Canal and the Shena Simon Campus of Manchester College (See Figure 2). The Garden itself is located within central Manchester and is bordered on all sides by extensive urban development (See Figure 1). Sackville Gardens are a public park within the city and they are used for general recreation by residents and visitors to Manchester. The Gardens are also, being part of Manchester's Gay Village, used for LGBTQ+ community events including Manchester Pride and the Sparkle Weekend (Hurcum and Morgan, 2025). LGBTQ+ related land use within the Gardens are not only confined to these participatory community events, as several LGBTQ+ memorials are located in the Gardens including the Beacon of Hope and Alan Turing Statue. The former National Transgender Memorial also used to be within Sackville Gardens, and within the excavation site boundary, before it was removed in 2022 following fire damage (Hurcum and Morgan, 2025).

The site is extremely flat, with the Gardens having been built on made ground at the start of the 20th century (Whyard, 2024). The Gardens are located at street level, and approximately 4m above the level of the Rochdale Canal. What materials were used in the construction of the made ground, and thus the geology of the park, was one of the research questions the community excavation hoped to investigate and was unknown prior to fieldwork commencing.

3.0 Archaeological Background

The location which would become Sackville Gardens is located outside of the historic core of Manchester, with late 18th century mapping showing the area was within the grounds of a large-high status house surrounded by fields. However, this area was eventually engulfed by the rapid industrialization of the city in the 19th century. The Rochdale Canal, which borders the present day Sackville Gardens on its North-Western edge (see Figure 2), was completed in 1804, connecting the Bridgewater and Ashton Canals and creating an East-West coast navigation for industry. By the 1830's the high-status house had been demolished and the fields which surrounded it were undergoing industrial development (Whyard, 2024). A branch off of the Rochdale Canal was cut at some point between 1832 and the surveying for the 1851 OS Map, bisecting the present day Sackville Gardens and flanked by numerous canal wharfs and the industrial buildings of the J. Whitworth & Machine Co. works. This canal arm would be infilled by the time of the 1891 OS Survey Map, with the J. Whitworth & Machine Co. buildings also having been mostly demolished, except for a singular remodelled canalside warehouse. Three new warehouses are also shown on Goad's 1899 insurance map in the park adjacent to Sackville Street (Whyard, 2024: 28; See Figure 2).

The site of Sackville Gardens was purchased by Manchester City Council in 1900 with the aim of providing a public garden in front of the new Manchester Central School (presently the Shena Simon Campus building of Manchester College) which was being constructed on the site of the former J. Whitworth & Machine Co. buildings. Construction of the garden was done in two stages, the first followed the demolition of the remaining industrial buildings in 1902, and the second stage was started at some point shortly after 1909, as shown by photographic evidence from the period (m05584; m05583; m58676), and the OS Map of 1908. These photographs, and one taken prior to the site's acquisition in 1898 (m05114), show the scale of the works and the depth of the newly made ground - elevating the entire site to the height of Whitworth Street (See Figure 2), approximately 4m above Canal level, where before there had been level access to the Canal on at least part of North-Western edge of the site.

The original layout of the Gardens has been somewhat lost over time. This original layout included several pathways which have since been removed/relocated, a decorative fountain which was removed in the 1950s, a Rain Gauge, decorative ornamentation, and a 1920s small shed which disappeared from photographs and mapping by the 1970s. Within the excavation area the National Transgender Memorial, and associated Memorial Garden and commemorative bench, were erected in 2013. The memorial was later removed in 2022 following its destruction by fire, however some fragments of the memorial were found scattered in leaf fall on site in December 2023 (Hurcum and Morgan, 2025).

Activity in the site pre-1800 has not been included in this report due the nature of the made ground on site which precludes the ability for a community excavation to reach archaeology related to earlier periods.

No previous archaeological excavation had taken place at Sackville Gardens, however an extensive history of the site was prepared by John Whyard of the Friends of Sackville Gardens for the purpose of the *Conservation Management Plan for Sackville Gardens* in January 2024. Further, Owen Hurcum and Colleen Morgan conducted an archaeological assessment of the National Transgender Memorial site in 2025, both of which the above section has heavily relied on along with further map progression by Hurcum during the initial design of the excavation.

4.0 Methodology

The aim of this excavation was twofold; a primary consideration for the excavation related to its place within the ‘Trowels, Trenches, #TransRights: Archaeology and Transgender Activism’ PhD project at the University of York. This aspect of the excavation, which concerned itself with means-testing policies for trans inclusion in archaeological fieldwork, is beyond the scope of this excavation report and is being prepared for publication elsewhere (Hurcum, in prep.). The other aim of this excavation related to a series of research questions designed in conjunction with the Friends of Sackville Gardens for the purposes of better understanding the history of the site by recording any archaeological remains discovered. These research questions were as follows;

RQ1: Were the ‘lost’ pathways buried, or were the paving stones lifted?

RQ2: What was the shed-like structure built from and what purpose did it serve?

RQ3: Does the made-ground on which Sackville Gardens was laid contain inclusions from the demolished industrial buildings which previously occupied the site?

RQ4: What is the level of preservation, if at all, for the industrial buildings which once occupied the site?

The excavation consisted of three trenches within the site boundary, and a surface collection of finds within both the site area and the Memorial Gardens situated adjacent to the site boundary fencing. The excavation work itself was carried out by a team of volunteers led by five supervisors affiliated with the University of York. The topsoil within trench areas was removed by hand and carefully monitored for finds. All exposed surfaces were cleaned by hand in order to detect any archaeological features revealed through textural or colour changes in the deposits. A sufficient sample of any archaeological features and deposits revealed were then excavated by hand in accordance with stratigraphic principles in order to satisfy the research questions of the excavation. Single Context Recording was used and a photograph record was maintained throughout the excavation. A full list of context descriptions, drawings, and photographs, is provided in Appendix 1. A list of Small and Bulk Finds recovered are presented within Appendix 3. A selection of photographic plates of the excavation are presented in Appendix 2.

5.0 Results

Figure 3. Trenches 1-3 and their situation within the site boundary.

5.1 Surface Finds

Surface finds from across the enclosed site area, and adjacent Memorial Gardens, were recovered on the first day of excavation. These finds predominantly consisted of fragments of the former National Transgender Memorial, with 12 segments being recovered by the excavation. This included several fragments previously identified in December 2023 by Hurcum and Morgan (2025: 119), albeit in a different location. Other notable surface finds also included a used condom, make-up sponge, and LGBT Foundation pin-badge, all of which align with the Garden's known role by the LGBTQ+ community for participatory events and use as a cruising location by patrons of the adjacent Gay Village.

5.2 Trench 1

Trench 1 was located in the north of the site extent and was situated to primarily investigate the 1920s shed-type structure (as seen in photograph m54271), with the potential of then coming down onto the

remains of the Canalside warehouse mapped in 1899 and shown in various photographs from 1902 to 1909 (m50114; m05583; m00714; m58676). Initially Trench 1 measured 4x4m, though a small area remained unexcavated due to impenetrable rooting and a minor extension was later added to the NE edge to determine the full length of (MC 1006)¹ (See Figure 3) - discussed in further detail below. As with all the trenches excavated, the first stage was the removal of topsoil (1001) by hand, which formed a patchy area of long grass within the shade cover of surrounding trees. The topsoil was dry and ran to a depth of generally around 0.05m. There was also extensive rooting in (1001), with roots often emanating from lower contexts, resulting in high likelihoods of floralturbation and the transference of artefacts (See Plate 06). Whilst most of the items recovered from (1001) were identified as 21st century refuse, such as plastic, drug paraphernalia, and glass, the top soil also contained at least one modern refuse item which could be positively dated to before 2000; a 1999 Walkers Crisps promotional Daffy Duck Quibix Jigsaw piece. Further, (1001) also contained several fragments of pebbledash render, a small quantity of 20th century ceramic, and a fragment of wired safety glass. It was interpreted that these finds related to two of the lower contexts, (MC 1006) and its fill (1010), and had been raised into the topsoil by a combination of bio- and floralturbation.

The topsoil overlaid a complex assortment of different contexts (See Figure 4). These were interpreted as being the foundation of the 1920s shed-type structure (MC 1006) and the fill of this structure (1010), a clay layer (1004) interpreted as recent build up of silted materials, a dry medium reddish orange silty clay (1005) interpreted as the infill for the lost Edwardian path of which Trench 1 overlaid, a fine dark greyish black silty sand (1013) interpreted as fill for an old planting bed, a firm dark black layer with significant chalk inclusions (1007) abutting the SE wall of building (MC 1006) interpreted as an external chalk floor, a coarse gravely context (1009) abutting the SW wall of building (MC 1006), and another fine chalk layer (1008) of similar, albeit finer, composition to (1007) adjacent to the SW edge of (1009). The latter two of which, (1008) and (1009), both being interpreted as different types of external floor surfaces. These contexts are all discussed individually below.

¹ MC indicates a 'Masonry Context'

Figure 4. Sketch plan of Trench 1 after removal of most of the topsoil and initial clean.

The uncovered extent of (MC 1006) consisted of two perpendicular stretches of masonry forming the corner of a small building within Trench 1. The SW to NE length of masonry ran for 4.1m before turning NW, with the SE to NW length running for 0.75m before meeting the trench edge. The masonry was excavated to a depth of 0.57m by the removal of (1010) which filled the area enclosed by (MC 1006). The base of (MC 1006) was marked with two 'steps' of bricks (See Figure 5; Plate 17). (MC 1006) was constructed using machine pressed red fired clay bricks of approximately 0.22x0.25x0.08m in size which were bonded with mortar. Identical bricks were also found in the fill of (1010), suggesting they originated from structure (MC 1006) and made their way into (1010) during/shortly after demolition. Several of the bricks removed from (1010) had maker's marks in their frogs reading 'Enfield Plastic Accrington'. The Enfield Brick & Terra Cotta Co. Ltd., who produced these bricks, was formed in 1893 and operated until 1938 when it was sold to another Accrington based brick manufacturer. These bricks are therefore datable to within this date range, which matches when the shed-type structure first appears on OS Maps in 1922. (MC 1006) has therefore been identified as the foundations to this structure.

The fill of these foundations (1010) consisted of a fine dark greyish black sandy soil which was excavated to the full depth of the foundations, but not further due to safety concerns, - approximately 0.57m in depth. (1010) had numerous inclusions with significant amounts of bricks identical to (MC 1006), as aforementioned, especially at lower levels in the deposit. 20th century ceramics were also found throughout (1010) as well as a second piece of safety glass, but of a slightly different composition to that found in (1001). Two fragments of roofing slates were also recovered from (1010) indicating the shed-type structure was slate-roofed, a detail not discernable from the scant images of the structure when standing (m54271).

Late 20th century detritus was found throughout (1010), with a higher concentration towards the top of the fill. Despite several confectionary wrappers being uncovered, no Best Before Dates were present, but dating was still possible through other means. The majority of datable material is from the 1970s to the early 1980s. Two Express Dairies Half-Pint 'Orange Crush' plastic containers were found which must be post-1972 owing to the patent number printed on their base. A Frozzy Freeze Pops wrapper was dated to between 1972-1978 by its manufacturer, Foskett & Sons LTD, who only operated under that trade name in that period. Further, a Greater Manchester Transport ticket wallet was recovered with the original 'double M logo' which first appeared in 1974. Additionally two Coke cans without barcodes, suggesting a pre-1978 date, were recovered. A Smiths Crisps Salt & Vinegar wrapper advertising their 1979 'Year of the Child' charity support provides additional dating evidence to the 1970s. A Princess Diana 1981 Royal Wedding Ale bottle cap and three TipTop wrappers, with identical examples contextually dated at another site to 1983 or before (Brophy, 2026: pers. comm.), provide the higher bounds of the dating evidence recovered in (1010), with these latter ones being nearer the top of the fill.

The shed-type structure, of which (MC 1006) was identified and which (1010) was interpreted as being demolition fill, last appears on the 1970 OS Map and "it is unknown when after 1970 it was removed" (Whyard 2024: 162). The artefacts recovered from (1010) during the excavation suggest a demolition date of around the early/mid-1970s, and likely no earlier than 1972. The later dated artefacts found nearer the top of (1010) indicate the fill was not immediately sealed with new turf and that the area was then used recreationally by patrons of the gardens after demolition, with their refuse working its way naturally into the upper parts of the demolition fill over time.

The shed structure was abutted by (1009) and (1007). (1009) was a coarse mid yellowish grey sandy clay gravel with significant gravel inclusions. It was not fully excavated during the excavation and therefore its depth was not ascertained. It abutted the SW wall of (MC 1006) and was interpreted as an external gravel surface contemporaneous with the shed-type structure. It separated the shed-type

structure from (1008) which itself abutted (1009) on the other side. (1007) was a firm dark black layer with significant white chalk inclusions that abutted the SE wall of (MC 1006) and was interpreted as an external chalk floor/pathway surface contemporaneous with the shed-type structure. It was approximately 0.02m in depth and acted as a sealing layer for everything below it. The full extent of it was not fully revealed during excavations.

(1008) was located on the far side of (1009) to (MC 1006) (See Figure 5). It was similar in composition to (1007) but was not a sealing layer, appearing instead to be a less defined 0.02m deep scattering of chalk and dark greyish black sandy silt over a layer of concrete (1018), and a posthole in said concrete [1012] (1011). (1008) was interpreted as dating to around the 1930s at the earliest due to its relationship to the lower contexts and their inferred dates. The uncovered extent of (1018) was 0.8x1.1m. It was interpreted as a concrete planter dating from around the construction of the shed-type structure primarily due the 1922 OS Map showing something in this approximate location next to the shed. A post-hole [1012], with fill (1011), was found in the corner of (1018) with dimensions of 0.2x0.2m and excavated to a depth of 0.3m, but it was not bottomed out. The fill (1011) was interpreted as being a gradual accumulation of top soil and contained no finds, and it was clear from the cut [1012] that the hole was formed as the concrete of (1018) set. It may potentially have been for a fence post around the perimeter of the planter.

(1005) was a medium dry medium reddish orange silty clay layer in the SW corner of the trench. It was approximately 0.10m in depth and extended towards Trench 3 where it was also identified and given the context (3003). The interpretation of (1005) will be discussed in tandem with (3003) in the section of this report detailing Trench 3 as the feature was excavated in full in Trench 3 and not in Trench 1. (1005) was, however, cut by [1014] and its fill of (1013). (1013) was roughly circular and consisted of a fine dark greyish black silty sand with occasional charcoal inclusions. It had significant rooting. [1014] was 0.6x0.6m where it cut (1005) in a roughly circular manner. It was interpreted as the remnants of cutting, and soil fill, made for the purposes of planting a tree or other large flora in the garden which has since been removed.

(1004) was a medium mid greyish orange silty clay, similar to (3004) in Trench 3, and within Trench 1 it formed an area approximately 2.5x1.5m along the SW edge of the trench with an un-cut edge against (1005). (1004) was fully excavated and had a depth of 0.1m. It contained no significant finds and had significant rooting. It was interpreted as a gradual natural accumulation of silty clay material over time. (1004) sealed part of (1019), which was also sealed by (1016) and (1007) in other areas of the trench (See Figure 5). (1019) was a medium mid-yellowish orange silty clay layer with occasional charcoal inclusions. It covered (MC 1020) and was interpreted as a layer which built up over (MC 1020) post abandonment.

Figure 5. Sketch plan of Trench 1 after (MC 1020) was exposed on the final day of excavation.

(MC 1020) was a masonry context of Victorian bricks roughly 0.25x0.1m on their uppermost face. They were bonded with lime mortar, with several large mortar patches visible in (MC 1020). The depths of the bricks were not ascertained as (MC 1020) was uncovered on the last day of the excavation and no time was found to excavate it out. (MC 1020) formed a solid wall, 3.25m long and 0.75m wide, that ran parallel with the SW edge of Trench 1 towards Trench 3 where similar bricks were found on the same alignment (MC 3022). The location, alignment, and structure of (MC 1020) and (MC 3022) match with the Canalside warehouse mapped in 1899 and seen in images from 1902 and 1909 (m50114; m05583; m58676). With a high degree of certainty (MC 1020) and (MC 3022) were identified as this Canalside warehouse. It was also inferred that (MC 1020) could not be the foundations of the building, which would have been some 4m lower and at the same height as the Rochdale canal, but rather the top of the basement wall. This suggests that during the demolition of the building in 1909 it was only removed to the level of the new landscaped gardens. This hypothesis

will have to be tested in a future excavation as (MC 1020) was discovered too late in the excavation to fully investigate. A small 0.5x0.5m patch of firm mid orange silty clay with frequent gravel inclusions (1022) was found abutting (MC 1020) on its external SW face. As with (MC 1020) it was not fully excavated and its depth is unknown. It was interpreted as a potential external floor that would have surrounded the Canalside Warehouse.

The chalk layer (1007), interpreted as an external pathway contemporary to the shed-structure (MC 1006), sealed two contexts; (1015) and (1016). (1015) was a medium mid yellowish orange silty clay with occasional CMB inclusions. Like (1007), it abutted (MC 1006) but did not extend the full length. It had a depth of roughly 0.12m and was interpreted as an earlier iteration of an external path to the shed. (1016) was a fine dry very dark black sandy silt with significant charcoal inclusions. It had a depth of around 0.04m. It was interpreted as being a construction layer for the chalk path (1007), where (1007) extended beyond (1015) and needed a new foundation. (1016) covered (1023), a fine mid-black sandy soil that only showed in section, and was similarly interpreted as part of the path construction layers. (1023) also partly covered (1019), discussed above.

(1015) covered (1017); a coarse mid grey silty clay context with frequent rubble inclusions of stone and bricks (See Figure 6; Plate 18). 1.5x0.75m of (1017) were exposed during excavation after (1007) and (1015) had been removed. It was not fully excavated during fieldwork, but it nonetheless yielded two interesting small finds. The first was a large chunk of glass slag, measuring approximately 0.13x0.12x0.9m and weighing 1.635kg, and the second was a small fragment of what was interpreted as melted window glass. Due the location of (1017) in the trench, being 'inside' the Canal warehouse (MC 1020), and the fact it was both sealed by (1007) and cut by [1024] - the cutting for the the foundations of the 1920s shed (MC 1006) - it was interpreted that (1017) was the demolition fill for the Canalside warehouse. There is no known glassworking activity in the historical record for the site and it was therefore interpreted that the inclusion of the large glass slag chunk in the demolition fill suggests rubble was imported, possibly along the adjacent Rochdale Canal, for the purpose of infilling and ground levelling during the second phase of Sackville Gardens construction following the demolition of the Canalside warehouse in 1909.

5.3 Trench 2

Trench 2 was located in the Eastern corner of the site, adjacent to a path laid in the 1970s and the park entrance to the Shena Simon building, formally the Manchester Central School (See Figure 3). Trench 2 was located to investigate one of the 'lost' original pathways, with the exact location of Trench 2 being dictated by three extant pieces of original path curbstone (MC 2005) which protruded through the modern topsoil (2001). The Trench was laid as a distorted 'L' shape, approximately 3x3m along

the NE and NW edges with a 1.5x1.5m step inwards on the SE and SW edge. However, due the extremely compacted and hard nature of the soil exposed after cleaning the full extent, it was decided to focus the excavation on a smaller area directly surrounding (MC 2005), a rectangular area roughly 2x0.75m. This rectangle was initially excavated using the box-grid method, with two boxes excavated on the path side of the curbstones (MC 2005) and one on the other (See Figure 6). Two of these boxes would then converge when one of the curbstones was removed for measurements.

Figure 6. Sketch Plan of the excavated part of Trench 2 at close of trench, with associated section sketches for the pathway construction layers.

There was no grass over Trench 2 and the top soil (2001) was a medium highly compacted dark greyish brown silty sand that was between ~0.1m to ~0.2m in depth. (2001) contained inclusions of glass bottle fragments, CBM, metal, plastic, including a piece of Lego, and an intact modern ‘Liquid

Gold' poppers bottle. Two fragments of architectural glass were also found embedded in (2001) either side of (MC 2005). (2001) primarily covered (2003) and (MC 2006), though it also covered (2002); a 0.16x0.12x0.05m course and weakly cemented dark yellowish brown patch of clay which was interpreted as a block of 'wallop' from either the construction of the original pathway or a later repair, and (2010); a medium compacted dark reddish brown layer interpreted as a deposit from the ground making of the park.

(MC 2006) consisted of a layer of individual fragmented partial flagstones that were embedded into the top of (2003), the largest of which was a broken corner measuring approximately 0.13x0.10x0.07m. The flagstone fragments recovered appear to match photographs of the finished Edwardian paths (m58675) and therefore it was interpreted that these were original flagstones for the path which had been left in-situ when the path was broken up and the flagstones removed in the 1950s.

(2003) was a fine friable dark brownish black silty sand of charcoal/ash like soil which sat underneath (2001), (2002), and (MC 2006). The layer was slightly cambered as it sloped away from the extant curbstones (MC 2005) towards the direction of the middle of the path, a feature concurrent with known Edwardian ornamental garden path construction methods (Rogers, 1910). (2003) was 0.07m at its deepest, where it had settled down the camber adjacent to (MC 2005), and was only around 0.02m at its shallowest atop the camber. (2003) sat atop (2004), also similarly cambered, an approximately 0.03m deep layer of medium dark yellowish brown sand. This layer was also interpreted as part of the Edwardian pathway construction. (2004) sealed (2007).

(MC 2005) consisted of the three extant curbstones of the Edwardian path that still protruded the modern top soil (2001). These were cut [2012] into (2010) and sat atop (2011) - a 'faux natural' compact dark yellowish brown clay with significant rubble inclusions interpreted as being from the ground making for the park in 1902 - and formed the curbing of the original Edwardian path. (MC 2005) abutted all construction layers of the path; (2002), (2003), (2004), (MC 2006); discussed above, and (2007), (2008), and (2009); discussed below. The middle of the three curbstones was removed for analysis and had a length of 0.42m, a width of 0.06m, and was 0.25m high, about 0.2m of which had been under the modern day surface. It was made from a light greyish brown stone and was consistent with the curbstones found in Trench 3 (MC 3005), and extant examples around Sackville Gardens where original pathways still stood.

Underneath (2004) was another layer of fine dark blackish brown charcoal/ash like silty sand (2007), similar to that of (2003). It was also similarly cambered, though unlike (2003) it had a consistent depth of approximately 0.03m and contained several Clay Pipe fragments; a rare find in Trench 2.

(2007) also contained a sheep bone which appeared to have been butchered (See Plate 04), deposited potentially accidentally during the pathway's construction - of which (2007) was interpreted to be a layer for. (2007) sat atop (2008) and (2009). (2008) was a coarse dark grey/yellowish brown clay interpreted as part of the path's construction. (2009) was a coarse compacted dark blackish brown layer approximately 0.12m deep which sat on-top of the 'faux natural' of (2011) in the cut of [2012]. (2009) had frequent inclusions of clay, rocks, CMB, and coal - material consistent with the 'hard-core' foundation layer of Edwardian ornamental paths (Rogers, 1910).

5.4 Trench 3

Trench 3 originally measured 5x5m, but was later extended by way of a 3x0.75m slot emanating west from the SW corner aligned with the pre-existing trench edge (See Figure 3), and was located just to the North West of the site center, about 5m away from Trench 1. It was situated to investigate the lost Edwardian pathway that ran through the site, the same pathway which Trench 1 found and Trench 2 was also investigating. Trench 3 was also situated to try and catch part of the Canalside warehouse. Trench 3 was covered in a medium wet rich dark clay grassy topsoil (3001), approximately 0.04m deep, with significant inclusions of contemporary refuse, which was removed by hand. (3001) covered (3002), (3004), (MC 3005), (3007), and (3010).

(3004) was a dark grey clay context which covered most of Trench 3. Two bore holes were uncovered in the context from previous soil sampling. These showed that, as best as could be observed, (3004) likely ran to a depth of at least ~0.5m. (3004) was not excavated. Small amounts of contemporary refuse, such as broken glass, was recovered from the top of (3004) during trench cleaning, objects which likely migrated down due to bioturbation. (3004) sits within the footprint of the Canalside warehouse and it was interpreted that it may be part of the demolition fill and subsequent levelling for the Gardens. Indeed, where (3004) was excavated to a shallow depth during the excavation of a long slot across the trench, a singular clay fired brick of 0.115x0.22x0.065m was recovered, similar in appearance to the bricks of (MC 1020). However, as (3004) was not fully excavated, this interpretation would have to be tested during another excavation.

(3007) was a fine dark brown context of soil with frequent clay inclusions which was uncovered during the extension to Trench 3. It had a defined edge with (3002), which it appeared to cut [3029], however this cut was only partially visible in section. (3007) was 0.26m deep and it was interpreted as the fill of a hole for a tree, or other large flora, in that location - similar to (1013). (3010) was a coarse reddish grey soil with sand and CBM inclusions around 0.75x0.75x0.05m which filled a cut [3030] into (3004), continued into (3024) underneath, on the SW side. It overlaid (3008) and (3017). Both (3008) and (3017) were fine dark brownish black loamy soil, differentiated mostly by texture, which

softly and irregularly transitioned into one-another. However, as this area of the trench was initially excavated by mattock, it is probable that if there was any defined edge this was lost, or even that they are the same context differentiated falsely as excavation switched to exclusively trowelling. The cut [3030] in which both contexts lay extended to a depth of 0.32m. It was interpreted that [3030], and the fills of (3008), (3017), and (3010), related to an Edwardian planter from the original garden layout. These were positioned within the grassy areas bordered by the pathways. The Edwardian, or otherwise early 20th century dating, was derived from two Edwardian glass medicine bottles recovered from (3008) and (3017); one in each. The bottle recovered from (3017) measured 0.02x0.02x0.11m and had side mold seams indicative of a bottle made in a cup bottom mold. The bottle found in (3008) measured 0.036x0.026x0.058m and was still sealed with the original cap and contained a reddish liquid. The bottle had a basal seam indicative of one created by a two-piece mold.

(3024) was a medium yellow clayish sand with frequent inclusions of grey clay, silt, fragmented CBM and mortar. It was 0.3m in depth. It covered the top of (MC 3022) - interpreted to be part of the Canalside warehouse due the brick's alignment and similarity with (MC 1020). (MC 3022) was not fully excavated, being uncovered on the last day of excavation. (3024) overlaid (3027), a coarse reddish black rubble layer with frequent CMB, stone, and rust inclusions. (3027) filled (MC 3022) on its 'inside' face and was not fully excavated (See Plate 12). (3024) also partly abutted (3023) where they both overlaid (MC 3022). (3023) was a medium dark brown firm clay context, excavated to a depth of 0.3m where the trench bottomed out, and contained extensive rubble fragments, including two large sections of Victorian clay drainage pipe. (3023) also contained two fragments of wired safety glass. These were different in composition to those recovered in Trench 1. The fabric of the recovered fragments suggests they were manufactured via a 'single pour' method over wire netting. Whilst this process was first tested in the UK in 1871, receiving a patent in 1887, it would not be commercially viable until a new process was patented in the US in 1892 (Kefallinos, 2013: 40) - a date that doesn't discount the possibility of them originating from the Canalside warehouse. (3023) was, as with (3027), interpreted as demolition rubble related to the destruction of the Canalside warehouse and ground making for the Gardens.

(3002) was a medium dry red sandy clay soil with inclusions of CBM, clay, and mortar. (3002) ran the full length of Trench 3 along the SW edge and was shown to be approximately 3m wide after Trench 3 was extended. As well as being covered by (3001), (3002) had a defined edge with (3001) where the topsoil ran slightly deeper over (3004) (See Plate). (3002) was also flanked by two curbstones (MC 3005), uncovered with the removal of (3001), of identical composition to those of (MC 2005). Given the location of (3002); being directly over the expected location of the Edwardian path, its alignment with (1005), the curbstones on its edge, its identical width to extant Edwardian paths in the park, and its composition, it was interpreted from early on as backfill from the removal of the Edwardian path in

the 1950's. However, based on dating evidence recovered from the lower context of (3003), this interpretation was shown to be incorrect.

(3003) sat wholly below (3002) and was primarily differentiated by texture as it was visually similar to (3002). (3003) was a highly compact coarse red sandy clay with more regular CBM, stone, and mortar inclusions than (3002). It ran to a depth of approximately 0.1m and abutted (MC 3005). Initially, as with (3002), (3003) was interpreted as relating to the lost Edwardian pathway (See Plate 03). At first it was considered to possibly be the 'hardcore' over which the flagstones were laid in 1909, however due to the dissimilarity with the path construction layers shown in Trench 2 for the same path, it was reinterpreted as being another demolition layer from the path's documented removal in the 1950s. This interpretation would be, however, also proved incorrect.

In the final few days of the excavation, as a deep slot approximately 0.75x5.2x0.6m was being excavated across Trench 3 (See Plate 14), a large contemporary plastic bag was discovered in (3003). The bag was fully intact and measured 0.33x0.23m, and bore the logo for "Olive Delicatessen". Olive Delicatessen was a deli formerly located on Whitworth Street overlooking one of the entrances to Sackville Gardens. The business seems to have closed around 2015, and the earliest mention of it comes from a January 2013 article for *Manchester Evening News* (2013). It was considered highly improbable that this bag could have migrated into the highly compacted (3003) through bioturbation and that it was far more likely to have been sealed in the context during deposition. This would date (3003) to around 2012-2015, post-dating when the Edwardian path in this location disappeared from OS maps by some 60 years. The disconnection with the path removal, and a far more contemporary date, was seemingly reinforced by the discovery of another plastic item in (3003), a small miscellaneous plastic wrapper with "Great Value" and "£3.6[?]" written on it.

This contemporary date posed more questions than answers. Especially as (3003) was removed and lower contexts were uncovered that were definitely related to the path construction; (3006), (3012), (3013), and (3015) - all within the path cut of [3032]. It could not be questioned that (3003) - and its overlay of (3002) - sat squarely over the Edwardian path, both due to the contexts covered and the fact they perfectly aligned with the original Edwardian curbstones of (MC 3005). The 'Olive Delicatessen' bag suggested the only other viable interpretation for why such a large amount of soil and debris would have ended up in this location in the early 2010s seemingly undocumented; for neither the Friends of Sackville Gardens or Manchester Park Rangers had any record of this as a discrete event. However, what is recorded is the construction of the formerly nearby National Transgender Memorial, memorial gardens, and access pathway, in 2013 (Hurcum and Morgan, 2025).

It was interpreted that the material excavated for the construction of the 2013 path to the memorial

was (3003) and (3002), being dumped by the contractors in a 'natural depression' in the park, potentially as it may have been prone to waterlogging as a result of the depression, rather than being taken away. This 'natural depression' was directly over, and caused by, the lost Edwardian pathway explaining why the modern layers of (3003) and (3002) perfectly aligned with the lost Edwardian pathway underneath. The construction date of the National Transgender Memorial lines up with the dating of the 'Olive Delicatessen' bag, likely from a workers lunch. An additional find from (3003), a singular large fragment of pebbledash render, measuring approximately 0.17x0.13x0.04, compacted into the context, also makes sense under this interpretation. Whilst the fabric of the fragment from (3003) is not identical to the pebbledash found in Trench 1, those finds show the shed did have pebbledash. It is therefore plausible that the fragment from (3003) was also from the 1920s shed - albeit from a different installation than the other fragments uncovered - and was disturbed and redeposited during the groundwork for the 2013 path which runs close to the shed's former location. Unless a further excavation, or a previously unremembered and undiscovered written record, demonstrates otherwise - this interpretation was considered the most likely explanation for these contexts - and for (1005) in Trench 1 which was identical and aligned with (3003).

(3003) overlaid (3006); a fine black layer of ashy soil and charcoal extending to a depth of approximately 0.1m. It was similar in composition to (2003) and was considered to be a similar, if not the same, path construction layer. Several lumps of yellowish clay with some coal inclusions (3013) were found sporadically at the point of transition between (3003) and (3006) and were interpreted as clay 'wallop' from the path's construction. Like (2003), (3006) overlaid a very fine greyish yellow sand (3012). (3012) was thinner than its counterpart in Trench 2, (2004), and was not visible in section. Resultantly it was uncertain at many points whether it was (3006) or (3012) that overlaid the lower contexts - a matter complicated by the jumbled and messy stratigraphy that appeared in section beneath this layer (See Figure 7; Plate 13). (3006)/(3012) overlaid (3025), (3015), (3026) and (3028).

Figure 7. Sketch, facing SE, of a section across Trench 3 and the extension.

(3015) was a coarse mid-yellowish clay with inclusions of CBM and fragmented bricks. It was somewhat similar to the 'hard-core' of (2009). (3015) was approximately 0.12m in depth and overlaid (3016) and (3019). (3019) was a fine yellow clay which contained several CBM inclusions. It also

fully encased a thin metal drainage pipe and was approximately 0.2m wide and 0.12m deep, with an exposed length that ran the width of the trench slot which exposed it; 0.75m (See Plate 11). A fragment of non-wired window glass and a singular broken piece of ceramic drainage pipe, different in fabric to that recovered in (3023) but identical to a fragment recovered from (2009), was also found in this context. (3019), which filled a cut [3031] of (3016), sat above (3020), also in [3031]. (3020) was a coarse medium dark brownish sand with CBM inclusions that was not fully excavated. These contexts were interpreted as belonging to the path construction, being a ditch excavated for the purposes of installing a drain for the path, before being backfilled and covered with 'hard-core'. (3016) was a firm yellow clay that was not fully excavated and interpreted as a 'faux natural', being a context deposited on site during the ground making of 1902.

(3025) was a coarse yellow sandy clay context with CBM, clinker, and rubble inclusions, approximately 0.15m deep. The path cut [3032] seemed to terminate at (3025), though it may have simply been lost during excavation by mattock. (3025) overlaid (3014); a near solid context of tar-ish coal around 0.12m deep. (3014) overlaid (3021); a medium yellowish red sand mixed with ground up brick with inclusions of larger CBM fragments. (3026) and (3028) were contexts only noticed in section. (3026) was a black greyish context of coal and sand, with some small clay inclusions. (3028) was a yellowish brown sandy clay context with CBM inclusions. As with (3016), these contexts; (3025), (3014), (3021), (3026), and (3028), were interpreted as depositions from the ground making in 1902.

6. Discussion

The two week community excavation at Sackville Gardens can be considered a great success, both in terms of community engagement and relation to the ‘Trowels, Trenches, and #TransRights: Archaeology and Transgender Activism’ PhD research project at the University of York, and how it related to the specific research questions designed in conjunction with The Friends of Sackville Gardens.

In relation to RQ1, *Were the ‘lost’ pathways buried, or were the paving stones lifted?*, evidence from all three trenches seem to suggest that the paving stones were lifted before the paths were covered up in the 1950s. It has been hypothesized (Whyard, 2024) that this was the case, with these lifted paving stones used in the ‘new’ paths of the 1960s/70s, and this can seemingly now be confirmed using the archaeological evidence.

In relation to RQ2, *What was the shed-like structure built from and what purpose did it serve?*, our excavations in Trench 1 have shed some light. The 20th century ceramic material culture recovered from the lower levels of the fill, and surrounding contexts, of the exposed shed foundations suggest it was likely to be a gardeners shed. Our excavations have also been able to demonstrate what the shed may have looked like in greater detail than the scant photographs depict. The shed had a footprint of approximately 2x4.2m, was roofed in slate, covered in a pebbledash render, and had wire-reinforced glass for its windows. It is likely to have had both the pebbledash render, and at least one window, repaired at some point owing to the different fabrics of these materials uncovered.

There was no record of exactly when the shed was demolished, only that it last appeared on OS maps in 1970. Our excavation has been able to suggest a date of around 1973-1975 based on materials recovered from the lower sections of the demolition fill.

In relation to RQ3, *Does the made-ground on which Sackville Gardens was laid contain inclusions from the demolished industrial buildings which previously occupied the site?*, our excavation was able to partly answer. It is clear from Trench 1 and Trench 3 specifically that a large amount of industrial rubble, possibly imported and possibly from the local demolition, was used in the construction of the made ground. Further investigations, particularly inside the footprint of the Canalside warehouse we exposed, would provide a greater detail of clarity for this question.

In relation to RQ4, *What is the level of preservation, if at all, for the industrial buildings which once occupied the site?*, our excavation was able to demonstrate that the walls of the Canalside building are

preserved to around the height of its cellar. This revelation encourages the potential for future excavations to investigate other buildings known to have stood on site, as the preservation of one suggests it is more likely that others have been preserved.

Whilst it should be considered that this excavation successfully answered the research questions it set out to answer, the excavation moreover proved the merit of community led archaeological excavations in Sackville Gardens. The success of this excavation shows the clear potential for future investigation into the Victorian industrial buildings. It is therefore hoped that future archaeological work can be undertaken at the park.

7.0 Acknowledgements

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8.0 References

8.1 Citations

Brophy, K. 2026. Email Exchange, January 21, 2026.

Hurcum, O. in prep. 'Excavations at Sackville Gardens – Running an Explicitly Trans Inclusive Community Dig in the Heart of Manchester's Gay Village', *Journal of Community Archaeology & Heritage*

Hurcum, O., and Morgan, C. 2025. "Now Our Remembered Are Forgotten" - An Archaeology of the National Transgender Memorial Site in the United Kingdom", in C. Fennell (eds.) *Combating Oppression with New Commemorations*, Routledge: New York, pp.115-131

Kefallinos, K. 2013. 'WIRE GLASS: HISTORY OF TECHNOLOGY & DEVELOPMENT', MSc Thesis, Graduate School of Architecture, Planning and Preservation Columbia University

Whyard, J. 2024. *A Conservation Management Plan for Sackville Gardens*

Manchester Evening News (2013) "Deli Review: Olive", *Manchester Evening News*, January 12, 2013,

<https://www.manchestereveningnews.co.uk/whats-on/restaurants-bars/deli-review-olive-1023851>

Rogers, W. S. 1910. *Garden Planning*, T Fisher Unwin: London

8.2 Photographs from Manchester Library Collection

m05583: Whitworth Street, Old building, rear Central Board School, 27/08/1902,
<https://images.manchester.gov.uk/collections/57547508-7df4-3432-ad07-44131c475fc5/?s%3Dm05583%26match%3Dor&pos=1>

m05584: Whitworth Street, Open space, 27/08/1902,
<https://images.manchester.gov.uk/collections/ae1a9f68-8338-3143-bdca-3772ce866afd/?s%3Dwhitworth%2Bstreet%26match%3Dor&pos=27>

m58676: Parks, Whitworth Street Park, Manchester, 1909,

<https://images.manchester.gov.uk/collections/c5c7b1f7-d0e3-387a-b114-040b9329aed8/?s%3Dm58676%26match%3Dor&pos=1>

m54271: Canals, Rochdale Canal, Canal Street, Manchester, 1960,
<https://images.manchester.gov.uk/collections/3b928f6c-6c69-3143-89ec-5ee0a0a24023/?s%3Dm54271%26match%3Dor&pos=1>

m58675: Parks, Whitworth Street Park, Seat, Manchester, 1909,
<https://images.manchester.gov.uk/collections/f06fb73c-8840-3731-a298-242edda57eb0/?s%3Dm58675%26match%3Dor&pos=1>

m00714: Canal Street Committee Property,
<https://images.manchester.gov.uk/collections/f2267718-fba2-3df1-97da-fbd9d1dda836/?s%3Dm00714%26match%3Dor&pos=1>

m05114: Rochdale Canal from Canal Street, showing Sackville Street Crossing Over, City Centre, Manchester,
<https://images.manchester.gov.uk/collections/0c7d7aaf-708e-3378-9f26-80e34a17a88e/?s%3Dm05114%26match%3Dor&pos=1>

Appendix 1: List of Contexts, Drawings, and Photographs

Appendix 1a: Contexts

Context Number	Trench	Description
(1001)	1	Topsoil
(1004)	1	Mid whitish grey silty clay
(1005)	1	Mid reddish brown silty clay with gravel inclusions
(MC 1006)	1	Brick Foundations for Shed-type structure
(1007)	1	Mid white chalk flooring
(1008)	1	Firm whitish silky clay
(1009)	1	Firm greyish brown silty sand with gravel inclusions
(1010)	1	Loose brownish black silty sand; demolition fill of shed-type structure
(1011)	1	Firm mid greyish black silty sand
[1012]	1	Posthole
(1013)	1	Dark black silty sand
[1014]	1	Cut of intervention in path
(1015)	1	Gray yellow layer on alignment of Edwardian path
(1016)	1	Black Soil below chalk
(1017)	1	Stoney/debris filled layer below (1016)
(1018)	1	Concrete Planter
(1019)	1	Mid yellowish grey
(MC 1020)	1	Brick wall of Canalside warehouse
[1021]	1	Construction cut of (MC 1020)
(1022)	1	Mid yellow fill
(1023)	1	Black layer of possible path
[1024]	1	Construction cut of (MC 1006)
(2001)	2	Topsoil
(2002)	2	Compacted clay
(2003)	2	Charcoal layer of path construction

(2004)	2	Sand layer of path construction
(MC 2005)	2	Curbstones
(MC 2006)	2	Path Flagstones
(2007)	2	Second charcoal layer of path construction
(2008)	2	Wallop/Compacted Clay
(2009)	2	Hardcore of path construction
(2010)	2	Dark reddish brown clay
(2011)	2	Dark reddish brown clay with significant debris inclusions
[2012]	2	Cut of (MC 2005) into (2011)
(3001)	3	Top soil
(3002)	3	Clay deposit beneath topsoil over path alignment
(3003)	3	Heavy sandy matrix with CBM over path alignment
(3004)	3	Dense Clay - 'faux natural' from Edwardian ground-making
(MC 3005)	3	Curbstones
(3006)	3	Black charcoal layer in path construction
(3007)	3	Dark soil with clay inclusion
(3008)	3	Fine dark brownish soft sediment - intermingled with (3017)
(3010)	3	Red sandy clay with CBM inclusions
(3012)	3	Sandy layer in path construction
(3013)	3	Clay with coal inclusions
(3014)	3	Solid coal deposit
(3015)	3	Clay deposit around (3014) with building material
(3016)	3	Solid clay beneath (3015)
(3017)	3	Dark clayish soil - intermingled with (3008)
(3019)	3	Fill around path drainage pipe
(3020)	3	Clay and charcoal underneath (3019)
(MC 3022)	3	Canalside warehouse brick wall
(3023)	3	Dark soil by (MC 3022)
(3024)	3	Yellow clay with debris inside (3022)
(3025)	3	Above (3014) in path cut

(3026)	3	Loose coal deposit with stone inclusions
(3027)	3	Sandy context with CBM inclusions and rust next to (3022)
(3028)	3	Clay and CBM layer
[3029]	3	Possible cut of (3002) by (3007)
[3030]	3	Cut of (3004) by possible planter, filled by (3010), (3008), and (3017)
[3031]	3	Cut of (3016) for Edwardian pathway drain
[3032]	3	Cut of Edwardian path

- Context Numbers that were equated or otherwise struck off have been omitted.

Appendix 1b: Drawings

Drawing Number	Trench	Description	Scale
0101	1	Site Plan	1:100
0102	1	Plan of Layer 1	1:50
0103	1	Plan of Layer 2	1:50
0104	1	Plan of Small Finds	1:50
0105	1	Plan of Layer 3	1:50
0105.1.1	1	Plan of Rubble Layer (1017)	1:10
0105.1.2	1	Plan of Rubble Layer (1017)	1:10
0105.2	1	Section of Masonry (MC 1006)	1:10
0105.3	1	SE Section through trench	1:10
0201	2	Trench 2 Plan	1:100
0202	2	Plan of (2001), (MC 2005), (MC 2006), (2002), and (2003)	1:20
0203	2	Plan of (2001) and (MC 2005)	1:20
0204	2	Plan of (2001), (MC 2005), (MC 2006), and (2004)	1:20
0206	2	Plan of Trench 2 at end of excavation with labelled corners for section drawings	1:20
0207	2	Section drawing Y-W	1:20
0208	2	Section drawing Z-Y	1:20
0209	2	Section drawing of Z-R	1:20

0210	2	Section drawing of X-W	1:20
0300	3	Small Finds Plan	1:50
0301	3	Trench Plan with contexts (3001), (3004), (3002)	1:50
0302	3	Trench Plan with contexts (3007), (3002), (3003), (3011)	1:50
0304	3	Section of Path (3003), (3006), and (3015)	1:10
0305	3	Section of Path (3003), (3006), (3014) and (3015)	1:10
0306	3	Section of Path (3006) and (3015)	1:10
0308	3	Full Section of Slot facing SE	1:20

Appendix 1c: Site Photographs

SG25 Photo #	Trench	Facing	Scale	Description	Plate #
Photo 0016	3	SE	10cm	Small Find 013 in situ	
Photo 0018	1	NW	1cm	Small Find 015 in situ	
Photo 0019	2	E	1cm	Small Find 019 in situ	
Photo 0020	3	NE	1cm	Trench Peg (Small Find 031) Erect in Soil	
Photo 0022	3	SE	1cm	Trench Peg (Small Find 037) Erect in Soil	Plate 01
Photo 0023	2	S	1cm	Small Find 044 in situ	
Photo 0024	3	SE	1cm	Blue Bottle Fragments (Small Find 039) in situ	
Photo 0025	2	N	10cm	First layer of trench 2 excavation showing contexts (2001), (2002), (2003), and (MC 2005)	
Photo 0026	2	N	10cm	As above, taken from an oblique angle	
Photo 0027	3	SE	50cm	Wide angle working shot of Trench 3	
Photo 0028	2	N	10cm	Second layer of trench 2 excavation, shows the partial flagstone fragments (MC 2006) in situ	
Photo 0029	2	S	10cm	Reverse shot of above	
Photo 0030	2	W	1cm	Small Find 057 in situ	
Photo 0031	Surface	S	1cm	Small Find 058 in situ	
Photo 0032	2	W	10cm	(2004) emerging through (2003)	

Photo 0033	2	SE	1cm	Small find 059 in situ	
Photo 0034	2	NW	1cm	Second layer of trench 2 after removal of flagstone fragments	
Photo 0035	2	SE	10cm	Working shot of Trench 2 primarily showing contexts (2003) and (2004)	Plate 02
Photo 0037	3	SE	50cm	Overview shot of Trench 3 showing the contrast between (3003) and (3004)	Plate 03
Photo 0038	2	NE	1cm	Small Find 063 in situ	
Photo 0039	2	SE	1cm	Small Find 066 in situ	
Photo 0040	3	E	10cm	The two soil sampling holes uncovered through (3004)	
Photo 0041	3	W	50cm	Overview shot of Trench 3	
Photo 0042	3	S	50cm	Overview shot of Trench 3	
Photo 0043	3	NW	10cm	Top of (3010) in (3004) - (3004) is labelled as (3001) in this picture	
Photo 0044	2	E	10cm	(2004) after being exposed in full	
Photo 0045	2	E	10cm	(2007) emerging underneath (2004)	
Photo 0046	2	SE	1cm	Small Find 079 in situ	
Photo 0047	2	E	1cm	Small Find 081 in situ	
Photo 0048	2	S	1cm	Small Find 083 in situ	Plate 04
Photo 0049	2	S	1cm	Small Find 084 in situ	
Photo 0050	2	SE	1cm	Small Find 092 in situ	
Photo 0051	2	W	1cm	Third layer of trench 3, primarily showing contexts (2008) and (2009) in plan	
Photo 0052	3	N	50cm	(3006) within the Edwardian path	
Photo 0053	3	S	50cm	Overview shot of Trench 3	
Photo 0054	2	W	10cm	(2009) 'hardcore' in Edwardian path	Plate 05
Photo 0055	2	W	10cm	Small box trench in Trench 2	
Photo 0056	1	NW	50cm	Overview of Trench 1 after removal of top soil	
Photo 0060	1	NE	50cm	Overview of Trench 1 after removal of top soil	Plate 06
Photo 0062	1	SE	50cm	(MC 1006) and (1007)	Plate 07
Photo 0067	2	W	10cm	(2010) on the 'outside path' side of	

				(MC 2005)	
Photo 0068	2	W	10cm	Oblique profile shot of (MC 2005)	
Photo 0069	3	N	50cm	(MC 3005) in situ	
Photo 0070	3	NW	50cm	Sondage in Trench 3 through path construction layers	
Photo 0071	3	SE	50cm	Sondage in Trench 3 through path construction layers	
Photo 0074	3	NW	10cm	The path cut of [3032]	Plate 8
Photo 0076	2	W	1cm	Small Find 129 in situ	
Photo 0077	3	NW	50cm	Section of Slot across Trench 3 with [3023] in right hand corner	
Photo 0079	2	E	1cm	(2009) at bottom of box trench within Trench 2	
Photo 0081	3	NW	50cm	(3008) (labelled as 3009), and (3016) in section	
Photo 0082	3	SE	50cm	Reverse angle of above	
Photo 0083	2	W	10cm	Fourth layer of Trench 2, showing the 'faux natural' of (2011) at base of path construction layers	Plate 9
Photo 0084	2	W	10cm	Trench 2 after removal of one the curbstones	
Photo 0085	2	W	10cm	(2011) at base of Trench 2 by Northernmost curbstone	
Photo 0086	2	W	10cm	Path construction layers in section	Plate 10
Photo 0087	2	S	10cm	(2001) and (2010) in section	
Photo 0088	2	W	10cm	Path construction layers in section	
Photo 0089	2	S	10cm	Path construction layers in section	
Photo 0090	2	E	10cm	(MC 2005) in situ after removal of path construction layers	
Photo 0091	2	SE	10cm	Path construction layers in section	
Photo 0092	3	S	10cm	Small finds 155 and 154 in situ	
Photo 0093	3	SW	10cm	Layers within [3032] after removal of (MC 3005)	
Photo 0094	3	W	10cm	Metal drainage pipe and fill at base of Trench 3	Plate 11
Photo 0096	3	S	NF	Working shot of (MC 3022)	Plate 12

Photo 0097	3	S	50cm	Cleaned section of Trench 3 slot	Plate 13
Photo 0098	3	S	50cm	Overview shot of Trench 3	
Photo 0099	3	SW	50cm	Overview of slot and extension in Trench 3	Plate 14
Photo 0100	3	NE	50cm	Section of path construction layers in Trench 3	
Photo 0101	3	NE	50cm	Overview shot of Trench 3	
Photo 0102	3	NW	50cm	Overview of slot and extension in Trench 3	
Photo 0103	1	NW	50cm	(MC 1020) after being exposed	Plate 15
Photo 0108	1	NE	50cm	(MC 1020) after being exposed	
Photo 0110	1	SE	50cm	(MC 1020) after being exposed with a clear shot of the 'inside' of (MC 1006)	Plate 16
Photo 0112	1	SW	50cm	(MC 1006) fully exposed with (1017) visible	
Photo 0116	1	SW	10cm	Excavated depths of (MC 1006) after sondage removal of (1010)	Plate 17
Photo 0118	1	SW	10cm	Rubble from (1017) in situ	Plate 18
Photo 0120	1	NE	50cm	Section of Trench 1	Plate 19
Photo 0122	3	W	10cm	(MC 3022) after removal of (3024), showing (3027)	
Photo 0123	3	NW	10cm	As above from different angle	

- Please note that post-ex images of finds are not listed here.

Appendix 2: Plates

Plate 01: A Tent Peg, Small Find 037, found erect in the soil.

Plate 02: Mid-Excavation Image of Trench 2 showing the curbstones and path construction layers. Scale 10cm.

Plate 03: Trench 3 showing primarily context (3003) to the right of a curbstone (MC 3005). This clear distinction and placement is why (3003) was initially assumed to be an Edwardian path destruction layer. Scale 50cm.

Plate 04: The butchered animal bone, small find 083, found in the construction layers of the Edwardian path in Trench 2

Plate 05: One of the box-cuts in Trench 2 near the end of excavation. The image shows the clear stratigraphy of construction layers and the hardcore base of (2009). Scale 10cm.

Plate 06: Photograph of Trench 1 showcasing the extensive rooting that covered the excavation extent in the trench. Scale 50cm.

Plate 07: The Corner of the 1920's shed (MC 1006) emerges in the trench with the external chalk flooring of (1007) visible in the right of the image and just above the leftmost ranging pole. Scale 50cm.

Plate 08: The Edwardian Path Cut [3032] (labelled here as 'F3000') in Trench 3, with (3002) and (3003) sitting in [3032] and above (3006). Scale 10cm.

Plate 09: Same excavated box as shown in Plate 05 after the removal of the 'hardcore' (2009), with the 'faux-natural' of (2011) at the base of the trench. Scale 10cm.

Plate 10: Edwardian Path construction layers visible in the section of Trench 2. Scale 10cm.

Plate 11: The Edwardian path drainage pipe in its cut at the bottom of Trench 3. Scale 10cm.

Plate 12: The Canalside warehouse (MC 3022) in Trench 3 with rubble (3023) to the right.

Plate 13: Section of Trench 3 across the Edwardian Path. Scale 50cm.

Plate 14: The slot excavated across Trench 3.

Plate 15: The brickwork of the 1920s shed (MC 1006), at the right rear, and the Canalside warehouse (MC 1020), foreground, in Trench 1. Scale 50cm.

Plate 16: Reverse shot of (MC 1006) and (MC 1020). The stepped bricks at the base of the 1920s shed are visible in the lower left. Scale 50cm.

Plate 17: The depth of the 1920's shed excavated by the removal of (1010). Scale 10cm.

Plate 18: (1017) with its excessive rubble debris and (MC 1005) cutting through it on the right. Scale 10cm.

Plate 19: A section of Trench 1 looking away from the exposed canalside warehouse. The external floor layers associated with the 1920s warehouse are clearly visible. Small Scale 10cm, Large Scale 50cm.

Plate 20: One of the Edwardian path curbstones (MC 3005) from Trench 3 after being lifted. Scale 50cm.

Appendix 3: Finds

Appendix 3a: Small Finds List

Find #	Context #	Material	Description	Notes
001	Surface Find	Wood	Transgender Memorial Fragment	
002	Surface Find	Wood	Transgender Memorial Fragment	
003	Surface Find	Wood	Transgender Memorial Fragment	
004	Surface Find	Wood	Transgender Memorial Fragment	
005	Surface Find	Wood	Transgender Memorial Fragment	
006	Surface Find	Wood	Transgender Memorial Fragment	
007	Surface Find	Wood	Transgender Memorial Fragment	
008	Surface Find	Wood	Transgender Memorial Fragment	NTM 001 in Hurcum and Morgan (2025)
009	Surface Find	Wood	Transgender Memorial Fragment	
010	Surface Find	Wood	Transgender Memorial Fragment	
011	Surface Find	Wood	Transgender Memorial Fragment	
012	Surface Find	Wood	Transgender Memorial Fragment	
013	3001	Metal	Possible Fence Top Loop	
014	1001	Latex	Used Condom	
015	1001	Cloth	Cloth Jewellery	
016	3001	Clay	Clay Pipe	
018	1001	Clay	Clay Pipe	
019	2001	Plastic	Plastic Button	
020	3001	Clay	Clay Pipe	
021	3001	Clay	Clay Pipe	

022	1001	Glass	Glass Marble	
023	3001	Plastic	Personal Adornment	
024	1001	Clay	Clay Pipe	
025	2001	Glass	Glass Bottle with Label	
026	Surface Find	Metal	LGBT Foundation Pin Badge	
027	3001	Clay	Clay Pipe	
028	1001	Clay	Clay Pipe	
029	1001	Clay	Clay Pipe	
030	3002	Clay	Clay Pipe	
031	3001	Metal	Tent Peg	Found Erect, pushed through lower contexts
032	2001	Glass	Architectural Glass	Same Fabric as Small Find 044
033	2001	Bone	Animal Bone - Mandible	
035	3001	Metal	Metal (Door?) Hinge	
036	3001	Glass	Glass Bottle Fragment with Logo	
037	3001	Metal	Metal Tent Peg	Found Erect, pushed through lower contexts - see Plate 01
038	3001	Glass	Glass Bottle Stop	
039	3001	Glass	Glass Bottle Fragments	
040	3001	Plastic	Plastic Button	
041	1001	CBM	Pebbledash Render	
042	1001	CBM	Decorated Building Material	
043	1001	Ceramic	Decorated Pottery	
044	2001	Glass	Architectural Glass	Same Fabric as Small Find 032
045	2002	Clay	Clay Compaction, 'Wollop'?	
046	MC 2006	Flagstone	Flagstone Fragment	
047	MC 2006	Flagstone	Flagstone Fragment	
048	MC 2006	Flagstone	Flagstone Fragment	
049	3002	Plastic	Plastic Tent Peg	Found erect, pushed

				through lower contexts
050	1001	Clay	Clay Pipe	
051	1001	Clay	Clay Pipe	
052	1001	Clay	Clay Pipe	
053	1001	Clay	Clay Pipe	
054	1001	Wire	Electrical Wire	
055	2001	Clay	Clay Pipe	
056	3002	Clay	Clay Pipe	
057	MC 2006	Flagstone	Flagstone Fragment	
058	Unstrat	CBM	Brick	
059	2003	Clay	Clay Pipe	
060	3002	Clay	Clay Pipe	
061	3002	Clay	Clay Pipe	
062	3002	Clay	Clay Pipe	
063	MC 2006	Flagstone	Flagstone Fragment	
064	Unstrat	Sponge	Make-Up Sponge	
065	2001	Plastic	Half a Plastic Button	
066	2001	Glass	Decorated Glass	
067	3007	Glass	Glass [Slag?]	
068	1001	Glass	Wired Glass Fragment	
069	1001	Glass	Decorated Glass	
070	1001	Glass	Glass with Label	
071	MC 2006	Flagstone	Flagstone Fragment	
072	1001	Plastic	Walker's Promo Item	
073	1001	Clay	Clay Pipe	
074	1001	Clay	Clay Pipe	
075	1001	Clay	Clay Pipe	
076	3001	Clay	Clay Pipe	
077	3003	Clay	Clay Pipe	
078	3003	Stone	Possible Flagstone Fragment	

079	2007	Flagstone	Flagstone Fragment	
080	3003	Clay	Clay Pipe	
081	2007	Flagstone	Flagstone Fragment	
083	2007	Bone	Animal Bone	
084	2007	Clay	Clay Pipe	
085	1001	Clay	Clay Pipe	
086	1001	Clay	Clay Pipe	
087	1001	Clay	Clay Pipe	
088	1001	Clay	Clay Pipe	
089	1001	Clay	Clay Pipe	
090	1001	Ceremic	Glazed Ceramic	
091	3001	Clay	Clay Pipe	
092	2001	Stone	Masonry	
093	3003	Clay	Clay Pipe	
094	3001	Clay	Clay Pipe	
095	3001	Metal	Metal Tent Peg	
096	1001	Glass	Decorated Glass	
097	Unstrat	Glass	Glass with writing	
098	Unstrat	Glass	Glass with writing	
099	1001	Bone	Animal Bone	
100	1001	Bone	Animal Bone	
101	3002	Clay	Clay Pipe	
102	1001	Bone	Animal Bone	
103	1001	Shell	Oyster Shell	
104	1004	Clay	Clay Pipe	
105	1010	Clay	Clay Pipe	
106	3003	Plastic	Plastic Bag	
107	3003	Plastic	Plastic Wrapper	
108	3003	Glass	Glass Bottle Neck	
109	1008	Clay	Clay Pipe	

110	3006	Glass	Architectural Glass	
111	3013	Clay	Clay Pipe	
112	3013	Ceramic	Ceramic Pottery	
113	3013	Brick	Brick	
114	3013	Brick	Brick	
115	2009	Clay	Clay Pipe	
116	1010	Plastic	Food/Sweet Container	
117	1008	Clay	Clay Pipe	
118	3003	Brick	Brick	
119	3013	Glass	Glass	
120	3008	Stone	Stoneware Pot Fragment	
121	MC 2005	Curbstone	Curbstone	
122	MC 3005	Curbstone	Curbstone	
123	1008	Ceramic	Ceramic Tile	
124	3008	Glass	Glass Medicine Bottle	Sealed and Contained a Red Liquid
125	3006	Concrete	Concrete Fragment	
126	1010	Alluminum	Coca-Cola Can	
127	1010	Alluminum	Coca-Cola Can	
128	1010	Clay	Clay Pipe	
129	2009	Metal	Corroded Nail [?]	
131	3009	Glass	Labelled Glass	
132	1010	Plastic	Toothpaste Tube	
133	1008	Cork	Bottle Cork	
134	1010	Clay	Clay Pipe	
136	2009	Clay	Clay Pipe	
137	2011	Brick	Brick	
138	2011	Brick	Brick	
139	3015	Glass	Glass	
140	3015	Shell	Shell	

141	3015	Bone	Animal Bone	
142	3015	Glass	Glass Bottle Stopper	
143	2009	Clay	Clay Pipe	
144	3015	Stone	Building Stone	
145	2009	Ceramic	Drainage Pipe Fragment	
146	2009	Shell	Shell	
147	1010	Bone	Animal Bone Fragments	
148	1010	Clay	Clay Pipe	
149	3015	Clay	Clay Pipe	
150	1010	Bone	Animal Bone	
151	3023	Glass	Wired Glass	
152	1010	Brick	Brick	
153	1015	Glass	Glass with letter	
154	3023	Glass	Wired Glass	
155	3017	Clay	Clay Pipe	
156	1010	Brick	Brick with Makers Mark	
157	1010	Textile	Stockings, possibly cut into a mask	
158	3008	Clay	Clay Pipe	
159	3008	Glass	Glass with Lettering	
160	3017300	Brick	Brick	
161	3013	Shell	Shell	
162	3017	Glass	Glass Medicine Bottle	
163	3019	Ceramic	Drainage Pipe Fragment	
165	1017	Glass	Glass	
166	3023	Ceramic	Ceramic Drainage Pipe	
167	1019	Glass	Glass	
168	3019	Glass	Safety Glass	
169	1017	Bone	Animal Bone	
170	1019	Clay	Clay Pipe	
171	1010	Glass	Wired Glass	

172	3019	Brick	Brick	
173	1019	Glass	Glass with Lettering	
174	1010	Glass	Glass Marble	
175	1022	Clay	Clay Pipe	
176	1010	Brick	Brick	
177	Unstrat	Glass	Glass Bottle Stopper	Found During Backfill
178	Unstrat	Glass	Glass with makers mark	Found During Backfill
179	3027	Chalk	Chalk Fragments	
180	3027	Metal	Corroded Metal	
181	3027	Glass	Decorated Glass	
182	Unstrat	Glass	Glass Bottle Stopper	Found During Backfill
183	1017	Glass Slag	Glass Slag	

- Small Finds that were 'struck off' during the excavation have been omitted.

Appendix 3b: Bulk Finds By Context

Context #	Bulk Find Classification	Individual Items Counted	Combined Weight (g)
1001	Nails	4	20
1001	Styrofoam	19	7
1001	Shells	1	8
1001	Plastic Bottle Caps	11	25
1001	N2O Canister	4	94
1001	Battery	1	21
1001	Glass Slag	13	130
1001	Coins	6	29
1001	Ring Pulls	16	9
1001	Charcoal	30	63
1001	Plastic Wrapping	52	10
1001	Ceramics	39	111
1001	Glass	266	721
1001	Glazed Ceramic	164	611
1001	Misc. Metal	17	563
1001	CBM	169	3737
1001	Plastic	122	107
1001	Metal Bottle Caps	28	83
1001	Slag	22	630

1001	Rubber Block	2	107
1001	Paving	14	1117
1001	Glazed Ceramic	17	9115
1001	Drainage Pipe	3	449
1001	Brick	6	1626
1001	Wood	1	25
1007	Glass	6	5
1007	Clinker	18	452
1007	Misc. Metal	7	221
1007	CBM	7	1659
1007	Glass Slag	30	531
1007	Ceramic	4	498
1007	CBM	1	65
1008	CBM	5	117
1008	Fabric	1	2
1008	Charcoal	1	2
1008	Plastic	5	24
1008	Glazed Ceramic	7	62
1008	Slag	1	151
1008	Drain Pipe	1	54
1008	Glazed Ceramic	7	7
1008	Slag	1	150
1008	CBM	5	118
1008	Plastic	5	21
1008	Fabric	1	<1
1010	Wire	4	18
1010	Metal Bottle Caps	10	30
1010	Cork	3	1
1010	Almond Shell	1	2
1010	Misc. Metal	10	415
1010	Slag	2	282
1010	CBM	70	1751
1010	Nail	1	13
1010	Ring Pulls	6	4
1010	Glass	142	931
1010	Clinker	3	42
1010	Plastic	127	85
1010	Coal	26	123
1010	Plastic Cups (White)	2	14
1010	Plastic Cups (Grey)	2	46
1010	Metal Bottle Caps	4	28

1010	TFGM Card Holders	2	9
1010	Wrappers	27	120
1010	Brick	21	242
1010	Slag	1	239
1010	Clay Drain Pipe	6	585
1016	Glass	1	3
1016	CBM	2	3
1016	Slag	2	47
1016	Glazed Ceramic	2	3
1016	Charcoal	1	3
1016	Plastic	2	2
1017	Glazed Ceramic	8	101
1017	CBM	92	3717
1017	Slag	21	2
1017	Misc. Metal	2	5
1017	Nail	1	19
1017	Metal Bottle Caps	1	3
1017	Plastic Bottle Caps	2	19
1017	Ceramic	2	70
1017	Wood	2	4
1017	Glass	15	47
1017	Plastic (Hard)	2	3
1017	Plastic (Soft)	5	1
1017	Coal	9	177
1017	Charcoal	8	96
1017	Ring Pulls	1	1
1022	Coal	2	32
1022	Charcoal	3	18
1022	Slag	2	107
1022	Burnt Wood	1	31
1022	Glass Slag	1	21
1022	Glazed Ceramic	1	4
1022	Glass	4	11
1022	Ceramic	1	4
1022	CBM	5	949
1022	Plastic	1	<1
1022	Charcoal	3	17
1022	Burnt Wood	1	30
1022	Glass Slag	1	20
1022	Ceramic	1	2
1022	Glass	4	6

1022	Plastic	1	<1
1022	Slag	2	106
1022	Glazed Ceramic	1	3
1022	Coal	2	32
2001	Slate	2	12
2001	Wire	1	2
2001	Glass Slag	3	2
2001	Wood	3	3
2001	Coal	12	23
2001	CBM	23	35
2001	Ceramic	7	8
2001	Glazed Ceramic	25	31
2001	Grout	13	65
2001	Ring Pulls	5	3
2001	Coin	1	5
2001	Sandstone	1	12
2001	Foam	1	2
2001	Nails	5	85
2001	Slag	5	126
2001	Metal Bottle Caps	2	4
2001	Plastic Bottle Caps	10	55
2001	Plastic	9	2
2001	Misc. Metal	9	134
2001	Plastic (Hard)	44	32
2001	Glass	290	248
2001	Ceramic	8	20
2006	Flagstone	2	92
2007	Glazed Ceramic	5	5
2007	Glass Slag	1	12
2007	CBM	6	22
2007	Glass	3	2
2007	Charcoal	3	2
2009	Glass	13	18
2009	Glazed Ceramic	8	42
2009	Slag	2	57
2009	Wood	1	1
2009	Glass Slag	9	33
2009	Ceramic	2	3
2009	Coal	3	14
2009	CBM	122	551
2009	Charcoal	52	48

2010	CBM	18	143
2010	Glass	5	12
2010	Misc. Metal	1	14
2010	Glazed Ceramic	3	3
2010	Charcoal	7	7
2010	Glass Slag	1	1
2011	CBM	4	239
2011	Slag	2	202
2011	Glass	1	1
2011	Glazed Ceramic	1	4
3001	Lighters	6	92
3001	Coins	8	49
3001	Glass	135	300
3001	Plastic Bottle Caps	15	58
3001	Metal Bottle Caps	42	126
3001	N2O Canister	2	48
3001	Shells	4	3
3001	Paper	1	2
3001	Ceramic	45	229
3001	Wood	29	51
3001	Slag	27	200
3001	CBM	75	678
3001	Textiles	4	5
3001	Charcoal	69	97
3001	Plastic (Hard)	109	105
3001	Plastic Wrappers	86	9
3001	Glazed Ceramic	62	127
3001	Misc. Metal	23	24
3001	Nails	13	38
3001	Battery	1	12
3001	Duct tape	11	7
3001	Grout	2	9
3001	Wire	1	8
3001	Ring Pulls	26	12
3002	Tape	1	3
3002	Rubber	1	13
3002	Wire	1	3
3002	Coins	3	11
3002	Nails	4	70
3002	Misc. Metal	3	9
3002	Plastic (Hard)	13	13

3002	Ring Pulls	9	6
3002	Clinker	7	17
3002	Glass Slag	8	33
3002	Glass	16	31
3002	Bottle caps	7	43
3002	Plastic (Soft)	21	5
3002	Glazed Ceramic	25	51
3002	Slag	10	63
3002	Slate	2	7
3002	Burnt Wood	15	19
3002	Charcoal	29	56
3002	Ceramic	30	102
3002	Wood	59	132
3002	CBM	265	1386
3003	Coal	49	121
3003	Wood	6	18
3003	Glass	10	13
3003	Glass Slag	16	242
3003	Polystyrene	1	<1
3003	Metal Bottle Caps	2	11
3003	Nail	1	4
3003	Misc. Metal	1	10
3003	Plastic	11	2
3003	Glazed Ceramic	14	62
3003	CBM	1017	7918
3003	Slag	58	651
3003	Clinker	73	232
3003	Paving Stone	3	395
3003	Coal	3	63
3003	Glazed Ceramic	1	18
3003	Plaster	3	18
3003	Limestone	4	126
3003	Plastic Wrappers	1	3
3003	Chalk	22	118
3003	Cinder	13	39
3006	CBM	59	339
3006	Glass	8	27
3006	Charcoal	9	26
3006	Misc. Metal	2	7
3006	Glazed Ceramic	3	8
3006	Plastic	1	<1

3007	Clinker	4	30
3007	Glazed Ceramic	1	4
3007	CBM	5	18
3007	Glass	1	3
3007	Charcoal	3	6
3007	Glass Slag	1	10
3007	Glazed Ceramic	1	3
3007	CBM	5	18
3007	Glass Slag	1	8
3007	Clinker	4	30
3007	Glass	1	2
3007	Charcoal	3	4
3009	Plastic	2	4
3010	Misc. Metal	1	4
3010	Glazed Ceramic	11	37
3010	Ceramic	5	37
3010	Glass	29	124
3010	Metal	1	3
3010	Slag	1	36
3010	Plastic	5	40
3010	Plastic Bottle Caps	1	5
3012	CBM	1	76
3012	Glazed Ceramic	1	10
3012	Glazed Ceramic	1	9
3012	CBM	1	78
3013	CBM	28	1196
3015	Glazed Ceramic	2	218
3015	CBM	20	819
3016	Glass	8	143
3016	Metal	13	88
3016	Glazed Ceramic	16	130
3016	Wood	1	<1
3016	Ceramic	2	23
3016	Coal	4	18
3017	Glazed Ceramic	2	18
3017	Clinker	1	13
3017	Misc. Metal	1	100
3020	CBM	7	340
3021	Glass	1	18
3021	Glazed Ceramic	1	4
3021	CBM	1	38

3023	CBM	6	277
3023	Coal	2	4
3023	Glass	7	184
3023	Glazed Ceramic	5	29
3023	Burnt Wood	1	9
3023	Misc. Metal	4	8
3023	Brick	2	1728
3024	Glazed Ceramic	2	3
3024	Glass	4	9
3024	Coal	2	4
3024	CBM	1	51
3024	Nail	1	38
3025	Clay Drain Pipe	3	636
3025	Glass	1	5
3025	CBM	1	4